

Leadership Behavior, Strategic Leadership and Instructional Leadership of School Heads: A Structural Equation Model on Teacher Engagement in Region XI

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine the best fit model of teacher engagement. Specifically, it established the interrelationship among school principal leadership behavior, strategic leadership and instructional leadership of selected schools in Region XI. Quantitative research design and structural equation model were utilized in this study. The data were gathered from the 400 teachers of selected schools in Region XI. There were four sets of survey questionnaires used in data gathering. Findings revealed that the level of school principal leadership behavior, strategic leadership and instructional leadership were high, and high for teacher engagement. There were significant relationships between and among school principal leadership behavior and teacher engagement, strategic leadership and teacher engagement and instructional leadership and teacher engagement. Importantly, parsimonious model suggested that school principal leadership behavior and strategic leadership and instructional leadership are drivers of teacher engagement of respondents in the study. Conclusive statements were drawn based on the findings of the study; the level of school principal leadership behavior is very high level. strategic leadership and instructional leadership correspondingly is high respectively. The level of instructional leadership is very high and the level of teacher engagement is high. On the other hand, there were significant relationships between the exogenous variable and teacher engagement. Furthermore, generated model 4 fits teacher engagement. This means that the causes of the teacher engagement lean on the, principal leadership behavior, strategic leadership which are stimulated by the academic leaders and educational advocates.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest problems schools face is how to deal with unmotivated teachers. The least engaged teachers expect the highest levels of engagement from unmotivated students, even if they themselves don't feel connected (Gobbi, Maltagliati, Sarrazin, Di Fronso, Colangelo, Cheval & Carraro, 2020). Teachers are creative beings. But when they lose their ability to create, many teachers lose the passion they brought to their profession. Teachers do not create good learning environments. They do not motivate students to participate. Unmotivated teachers can drool over teacher manuals (Blume, C. (2020)

Admittedly, positive teacher behaviors are important and suggest ideas for effective engagement. Certain behaviors, such as spending more time preparing lessons or spending more time in tutoring, encourage student-teacher engagement. However, examining engagement as a psychological property or attitude provides added value and

allows for a deeper understanding. Teachers who have positive attitudes toward students and who believe in the importance of the educational process are more likely to take actions related to increasing teacher engagement, thereby positively affecting student psychology, giving and promoting student involvement in the classroom environment (Cryrakides)., Antimow and Panaiotou, 2020).

The external pressures created by the NCLB clearly require different knowledge and strategic skills from today's top leaders. The fact that current research identifies leadership behavior of school leaders as one of the most important determinants of student performance highlights the need for a holistic understanding of the role of teachers in schools. clearly (Shukla, Kuril, Chand, 2020).

Given the importance of leadership and the recognition of the central role that school leaders play in school efficiency, it is not surprising that researchers have devoted themselves to investigating different qualities of leadership. and management factors as these were found to produce results in their subordinates. Hence, it was revealed in previous studies that leading the school with innovative edge managing and valuing diversity and favorable individual's attitudes toward the organization (Cunningham, Hazel, & Hayes, 2020) contribute to work outcomes (Benmira & Agboola, 2021).

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Leadership Behavior of School Heads

Educational leadership is perhaps the most important factor in an effective learning environment (Rehman, Shahzad, Farooq, & Javaid, 2020), initiates improvements in schools, creates a learning-oriented educational climate, and promotes educational leadership. Inspire and supervise teachers to perform their duties as effectively as possible. The primary role of school leaders is to promote effective teaching and learning, with the overall goal of improving student achievement (Kelemen, Matthews & Breevaart, 2020).

Similarly, education today requires leaders who are motivated to advance student achievement in the most complex environments. Leaders can create this environment by establishing policies that emphasize purpose, offer students choices in the classroom environment, and reward student achievement. Leaders can play an important role in developing versatile students (Ozdemir, Sahin & Ozturk,

2020). School leaders are individuals who hold various roles within a school and exert influence and leadership to achieve school goals (Zaini & Syafaruddin, 2020). An educational leader is a person whose actions (both administrative and pedagogical) are intentionally designed to influence the primary direction of the school and, ultimately, student performance.(Cheng, Guo, & Lin, 2020).

The first domain of Leadership Behavior is management-school goals. Principals who scored high on this indicator often took actions to manage school operations in line with the school's goals and to ensure that teachers' instruction in the classroom achieved the goals. direct focus. These school leaders also tend to use student achievement levels and test results to set goals and drive curriculum development (Guntner, Klonek, Lehmann-Willenbrock, & Kauffeld, 2020).

Additionally, school leaders strive to ensure clarity within schools about their responsibilities for coordinating the curriculum. School leaders who scored highly on this indicator reported that they were more likely to ensure that their teachers' professional development activities were consistent with the school's goals and curriculum (Totororella, van Dun, de Almeida, 2020). School leaders also played a key role in integrating external and internal accountability systems, helping teachers align instruction with agreed learning goals and performance standards. Aligning instruction with external standards, setting school goals for student performance, measuring progress against those goals, and adjusting school programs to improve performance are other important aspects of school governance. have been identified (Mickson and Anlesinya, 2020).

Her third area of leadership behavior is direct supervision of school instruction. Principals who perform well on this indicator often use direct observation of teachers' teaching practices to make suggestions to teachers on how to improve teaching in the classroom. These principals also often supervise the academics and work of their students (Ozgenel & Aksu, 2020). Actions focused on effective school leader instruction include: supporting teachers' teaching methods, adapting approaches and materials to meet student needs; allocating resources and materials; Includes frequent visits. Teaching evaluation activities of school leaders include frequent classroom visits to collect and provide feedback on teaching methods and materials (Akbiyik, Korhan, Kiray, & Kirsan, 2020).

The fourth is responsible management. As one of the most important issues in education policy today, accountability is a key factor in the success of any educational improvement system. It is literally a process by which students, teachers and administrators report their progress. Accountability is the means by which policy makers, parents and taxpayers at the state and county level monitor student and school performance (Hidayat and Wulandari, 2020).). School leaders who score highly on this indicator see it as their job to hold schools accountable to stakeholders both within and outside of their schools. Their job is to teach new teachers teaching methods approved by the Minister and to ensure that all teachers take responsibility for improving their

teaching skills. These principals also focus on convincing parents of students of the need for new ideas and practices in schools (Demirhan, 2020).

In the 21st century, the ability to work in teams has become essential. Internationally, team performance determines market success. But teamwork has a long history. It is one of the oldest human habits still in use today and is not limited to the corporate realm. Interestingly, humans have worked together in groups and teams since the dawn of civilization. Cooperation leaves a mark virtually everywhere. On the other hand, it is claimed that the first official studies on cooperation were conducted during World War II and were primarily concerned with figuring out why military teams failed. (Jahroni, Lestari, Mardikaningsih, 2020).

The first area concerns coordination. Teamwork is essential for an organization to be successful and profitable. One of the advantages of working in a team is that the workload can be shared by all members of the team. Working in a team benefits individuals, teams and companies alike. Teamwork can increase the effectiveness of a school's learning environment. Most teacher professional development programs seem to pay little formal attention to collaborative skills (Miller, Slater & Turner, 2020).

Collaboration is a resource that can be used to advance the standard of teaching and learning. This can be seen, for example, in team teaching, where it promotes teacher interaction and improves the quality of teaching and learning. The power of the teachers is linked and bundled. (Loverag, Loric, Nuwafor, Van Bogart & Cummings, 2020). The second area concerns decision making. His second question, often raised in relation to school leadership, is what groups should play a role in school decision-making, and to what extent schools should focus on teaching and learning. It has been a long-standing goal of many school reformers to give teachers a key role in leadership and decision-making in schools, especially outside the classroom. In recent years, expanding the role of teachers in schools has become a focus of teacher leadership initiatives (Thrasher, Biermeier-Hanson & Dickson, 2020).

As demonstrated in team teaching, collaboration facilitates teacher-to-teacher interaction, which can lead to better teaching and learning. Address teacher weaknesses while integrating their strengths. Other team members can monitor underperforming teachers, criticize them, and suggest changes in a safe and encouraging environment. Collaboration within the enterprise is therefore important and improves work performance and outcomes, but its lack has a negative impact on teaching and learning in schools (Roundy, 2020).

B. Strategic Leadership

Strategic leadership is based on long-term planning. This includes system setup and maintenance, resource allocation, and vision communication. School leaders must have a clear focus on the central vision of the school. Strategic leadership is defined as a leader's ability to anticipate, foresee and maintain flexibility and empower others to effect strategic change when necessary (Al Thani & Obeidat, 2020).

As a result, strategic leaders can set the vision and direction for organizational growth and success. To successfully manage change, managers need the skills and tools to both develop and execute strategy. Managing change and uncertainty requires strategic leaders who can provide direction and build ownership and alignment in implementing change (Luciano, Nahrgang & Shropshire, 2020).

In particular, the fact that a manager's strategic leadership style leads to organizational effectiveness is an undeniable argument. Therefore, in order to become a goal-oriented manager, we must re-evaluate the goals and values of the school organization to successfully execute them, so that teachers as practitioners can apply creative thinking to their own work as well. (Golensky & Hager). , 2020).

The first area is the target frame. School goal setting is the role of school leaders in determining areas where school personnel will focus their attention and resources during a particular school year. Effective school leaders also ensure that the idea of academic success for all is accepted by faculty and staff and support a school-wide learning improvement agenda focused on student progress goals (Kurzahls, Graf-Vlachy & König, 2020).

Meanwhile, instructionally effective schools often have Well-defined goals that focus on student achievement. The focus is on reducing goals that can mobilize staff energy and other school resources. Several coordinated goals, each within a manageable range, seem to be most effective. Goals should include data on past and current student performance and staff responsibilities for achieving goals. The opinions of teachers and parents seem to be important when developing school goals. Goals should be expressed in measurable terms (teachers are responsible for providing guidance in defining school goals). Therefore, staff and teachers should also be involved when developing school goals, as their experiences form the basis of school goal setting. In addition, involved staff also provide other important information relevant to their experience in defining school goals (Nwachukwu & Vu, 2020).

Additionally, effective leaders involve employees in setting and defining school goals that are implemented and evaluated at the end of the school year. This situation reinforces efforts to reach school goals. Therefore, with a clear vision and mission, and the commitment of teachers, there is confidence that any school can succeed (Derrington & Sanders, 2011).

The second indicator is the communication of school goals. When defining school goals, school leaders should communicate the school goals to the school community. Communicating and explaining the goals of the school is one of her principal duties as a teacher. Clear goals and high expectations widely shared in the school community are among the hallmarks of effective schools (Alkheyi, Khalifa, Ameen, Hossain, Hewedi, Nasir, 2020). School leaders ensure that the importance of school goals is understood by regularly discussing and reviewing them with staff throughout the school year, especially in the context of education, curriculum and budgetary decisions. I can. Communication includes formal communication (e.g., goal

statements, staff memos, principal or city council newsletter articles, curriculum and staff meetings, parent-teacher conferences, school handbooks, assemblies) and informal interactions (e.g., (e.g. conversations with staff) are included. School mission (Walden, Lie, Pandolfo & Nemme, 2020).

The third area is instruction monitoring and evaluation. Supervision becomes a positive process that leads to feedback throughout the school year. Supervision is daily instruction to improve lessons. Supervisors are encouraged to visit the building as often as possible and make both formal and informal observations of the three domain areas (Tirastittam, Jermittiparsert, Waiyawuththanapoom, & Aunyawong, 2020).

Principal supervision parallels teacher supervision as more A formative one through observation, feedback, and professional development opportunities, and a cycle of continuous improvement, "more of a process than an event." Like teachers, school leaders need accurate feedback from assessment systems to meet district expectations and student improvement goals. Tetic, 2020).

The second metric is driving improvement. Within schools, school leaders are in a unique position to influence the implementation of these Guiding Principles and influence the overall quality of teacher professional development. One of her primary responsibilities of a school leader is to create and maintain a positive and healthy teaching and learning environment for everyone within the school, including professionals (Amayreh, 2020). Moreover, the ability of school leaders to influence school structure, culture and mission is well documented. Building a vibrant and successful learning community is a collaborative effort by all school staff. The leadership of school leaders in the area of teacher professional development is essential to the creation and success of school learning communities (Sibghatullah & Raza, 2020).

Above all, strategic leaders must find the best and easiest way to deal with problems when they arise. Factors influencing strategic leadership depend on the occupations and activities that administrators who need to encourage personal skill development in schools should pursue (Meehan & Jonker, 2020). Guidance direction.

Principals and principals continue to strive to maintain balance and competence in their role as teachers. Lack of comprehensive training is cited as the reason for the lack of competence in schools and the lack of emphasis on educational leadership. Insufficient time to conduct classroom activities, unrealistic community expectations, and excessive paperwork have also been cited as reasons for the shortage (Johnson, 2005).

Instructional leadership includes setting clear goals, managing the curriculum, monitoring lesson plans, allocating resources, and conducting regular teacher assessments to facilitate student learning and development. Teaching quality is a top priority for faculty. Educational leaders focus on their core business of teaching, learning and knowledge. Staff should meet regularly to discuss how they can improve their work and ultimately help students learn more effectively (Lash, 2010).

For school leaders to be truly successful in their leadership role, they must strive to free themselves from the bureaucratic aspects of education. They need to redouble their efforts to improve their learning and teaching methods. Needless to say, improving teaching methods is a goal worth striving for (Miczo, 2009). The first area in leadership practice is excellence in that area. High-performing schools with high poverty levels provide a "protective factor" that helps build student-school bonds. These factors include fostering loving relationships between adults and children and among peers, setting high expectations and providing the support needed to meet those expectations (Cooley & Shen, 2010).

The ability of school leaders to select faculty and staff is central to their ability to establish a school culture and the ability to promote better student achievement. Teacher responsiveness can be hampered if school leaders are not involved in the hiring and firing of teachers, and if school leaders do not have a say in the selection of staff, learning outcomes may suffer. difficult to hold accountable.

School leaders therefore play an important role in strengthening relationships between school personnel and their surrounding communities (Fullan, 2001). The most successful school leaders in difficult situations tend to have strong ties and trust with school parents and the wider community (Fancera & Bliss, 2011).

In particular, school leaders must learn how to self-acquire new forms of education and monitor and improve teachers' new practices. Additionally, she initiates activities and embodies the collective responsibility and leadership of the group. They must become learning leaders responsible for building communities for professional practice. Methods of assessment and professional development require more sophisticated applications, and school leaders should incorporate them into the structure of working hours (Justice & Kaderavek, 2010). A second area of leadership practice is self-awareness. Much is known about the challenges faced by school leaders who play a central role in schools. Coping with multiple responsibilities and changing priorities is a common challenge for school leaders. Challenges such as reforming curricula and standards, school outcomes, student guidance, and parental and community expectations are almost universal across states and countries (Hallinger, 2010).

Successful leadership therefore requires competent school leaders with strong effectiveness, experience and knowledge in all areas of responsibility. Without relevant knowledge of special education, school leaders find it difficult to professionally develop staff in the special education department and involve them in school initiatives (Hoy & Tarter, 2011).

Given that people who can make others laugh can make them hear almost anything they have to say, the use of humor in dealing with people, especially in professional settings, is highly valued by school leaders and others. There are many advantages for leaders of Psychological benefits of using humor in communication have been shown to include reduced stress, reduced anxiety, increased motivation, and the

formation of stronger connections between speakers and listeners (Kim, Ham, & Paine, 2011).

Moreover, if school leaders can develop such relationships and win teachers' loyalty and trust, their job satisfaction may also improve. Regular use of humor and laughter can enhance the ability of principals to develop meaningful relationships with faculty and staff. Hurren (2010) found that skillful use of humor by school leaders also promoted a positive school climate, increasing the effectiveness of school-wide programs and other initiatives (Klassen & Chiu, 2010).

Her third area of leadership practice is strategic thinking. Principals also mentioned strategies beyond classroom observation to help teachers learn and develop professionally. One such strategy was to provide teachers with what some principals called "strokes." Not all school leaders used the term, but all emphasized the importance of giving teachers individual assessments (Main & Hammond, 2008).

Strategic thinking results in the creation of unique business insight. Leaders who achieve this are leaders who broaden their thinking and look beyond the basic elements of their organization. Effective leaders are thought leaders, business strategists, and managers of talent, expectations, and harmony in the workplace (Moolenaar, Slegers & Daly, 2012).

Her fourth area of leadership practice is the ability to build relationships. Effective school leaders put student success at the center of their work and, accordingly, pay attention to, communicate and prominence student mastery of the school, instruction, curriculum and learning objectives. . Learning needs to occur throughout an organization, and principals need to become participants in the learning process in order to shape and encourage the implementation of effective learning models in their schools (Rosnarizah, 2015).

In addition to learning about the community, principals believe that teachers need to learn about the conditions of students' home-life, and develop skills for involving the parents and maybe older siblings of students to help them succeed in school Likewise, the fifth domain in leadership practices willingness to help others succeed. Effective principals work relentlessly to improve achievement by focusing on the quality of instruction. They help define and promote high expectations; they attack teacher isolation and fragmented effort; and they connect directly with teachers and the classroom also encourage continual professional learning (Yu, Luo, Sun, & Strobel, 2012).

Notable, principals themselves agree almost unanimously on the importance of several specific practices, according to one survey, including keeping track of teachers' professional development needs and monitoring teachers' work in the classroom (Witziers, Bosker, & Kruger, 2011). A constant desire to learn is the fifth domain. Professionals in school leaders say that robust and ongoing training can reduce these problems and help keep them in the business, but professional development of school leaders is essential for other areas such as teacher education. They say they are often ignored because of pressing needs. And the quality of

professional development received by many school leaders is questionable (Quinn, 2012).

The ability of school leaders to influence school structure, culture and mission is well documented. Building a vibrant and successful learning community is a collaborative effort by all school staff. The leadership of school leaders in the area of teacher professional development is critical to the creation and success of school learning communities (Murphy, Elliott, Goldring & Porter, 2007).

Communication skills are the last area. Teacher leadership is demanding and complex, requiring excellent cognitive and communication skills. Leadership encompasses a wide range of areas, including curriculum implementation, teacher support and supervision, teacher coaching, and classroom observation (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

Principals do much of their day-to-day work through verbal and interpersonal communication, or conversation. In their day-to-day interactions with teachers, school leaders emphasize how improving teacher learning and classroom practice impacts student learning, help build a positive perspective. School leaders have high expectations of learning and professional practice (Leithwood, Day, Sammons, Hopkins & Harris, 2006).

C. Teacher Engagement

A high level of teacher engagement, which is defined as Commitment and enthusiasm are essential for secondary school success and contribute to academic success (Basikin, 2007). Kirkpatrick (2007) described workplace engagement as an employee's interest, enthusiasm, and investment in their work. Maslach, Schaufeli, and Leiter (2001) defined engagement as energy, commitment, and effectiveness.

However, this definition differs from that of his Schaufeli et al. (2002) define engagement as "a positive and fulfilling work-related state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication and commitment". Enthusiastic teachers are concerned about the quality of the education they provide. Enthusiastic teachers explore new ideas, implement best teaching practices, modify teaching methods to meet the instructional needs of their students (Cotton, Dollard, & de Jonge, 2002), have high expectations of their students, Take responsibility for student learning, monitor student progress regularly, and provide feedback to students (Marzano, 2003).

Attitude features give engaged teachers a connection with students that goes beyond mere behavioral expression by performing actions in the classroom. Enthusiastic teaching therefore reflects a person's more ingrained inclinations towards work. It is the teacher who believes in and promotes the idea that education comes first, taking on the role of educator committed to transforming the lives of students (Lieberman & Miller, 2001).

It is important for teachers to feel confident that their efforts are effective and making a difference in the lives of their students. The work of effective and enthusiastic teachers is fueled by the significance of the success of the work itself. Enthusiastic teachers feel pride and confidence in their efforts when their students achieve something, but experience disappointment and new challenges when they fail. In

addition, enthusiastic teachers are characterized by enthusiastic and active interest in energetic work (Basikin, 2007).

The first area of teacher engagement is cognitive engagement. Cognitive engagement reflects not only the student's approach to academic tasks, but also psychological engagement and willingness to master complex concepts (Fredricks et al., 2004). Specifically, the concept of cognitive engagement draws on goal orientation, the use of cognitive strategies, and self-regulation theories that have historically been associated with motivational processes and academic functions (Cleary & Zimmerman, 2012; Wolters & Taylor, 2012).

Similarly, enthusiastic teachers explore new ideas, implement best teaching practices (Marzano, 2003), modify instruction to meet the teaching needs of their students (Cotton, Dollard, de Jonge, 2002), and have high expectations of (Boaler, 2002). . 2004; Tyler & Boelter, 2008), take responsibility for student learning (Cotton et al., 2002), frequently monitor student progress, and provide feedback to students (Marzano, 2003).

Cognitive Engagement teachers differentiate instruction to meet the specific instructional needs of students, introduce different instructional strategies, and use data to inform instruction. Emotionally involved teachers understand that building positive relationships with students is a prerequisite for student engagement, not just getting to know them superficially.

Emotional engagement is the next area. However, examining engagement as a psychological property or attitude provides added value and allows for a deeper understanding. Teachers who have a positive attitude toward students and believe in the importance of the educational process are more likely to take actions related to increasing teacher engagement, thereby positively affecting student psychology. and promote student involvement in the classroom environment (Maslach), , & Head, 2008).

The third area is social commitment. Maintaining a positive relationship is also part of engagement. Most students do not perform at their best in class when they feel that their teachers are not paying attention to them. Building a teacher-student relationship is essential to creating an engaged classroom. Teachers can begin building relationships with students by taking an interest in them, knowing their names, and talking to them both inside and outside the classroom (Balducci, Fraccaroli, & Schaufeli, 2010).

In its broadest sense, creating an environment that fosters enthusiasm and engagement is another element of engagement. A quality education can take place in a variety of settings. However, there is no doubt that a well-designed and maintained classroom has a positive impact on student participation. Classrooms should be physically comfortable for students in terms of temperature, space, furnishings and structural organization (Adekola, 2010).

The foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures had helped bring into focus the school principal leadership behavior and strategic leadership as well as the level of instructional leadership on teacher engagement.

The literature presented had also helped the researcher realized that school principal leadership behavior and strategic leadership as well as the level of instructional leadership has a great influence on teacher engagement.

D. Structural Equation Model

Structural equation modeling encompasses a broad array of models from linear regression to measurement models to simultaneous equations, including along the way confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), correlated uniqueness models, latent growth models, multiple indicators and multiple causes (MIMIC) models, and item-response theory (IRT) models (MacCallum & Austin, 2000). Stein and Nyamathi (2000) added that a structural equation model implies a structure of the covariance matrix of the measures hence, an alternative name for this field is "analysis of covariance structures". Once the model's parameters have been estimated, the resulting model-implied covariance matrix can then be compared to an empirical or data-based covariance matrix. If the two matrices are consistent with one another, then the structural equation model can be considered a plausible explanation for relations between the measures (Longshore & Galaif, 2003). One advantage of Structural Equations is that it provides an integration facility, a single method screen between major programs. This helps researchers more accurately specify hypotheses and operationalizations of constructs. Consider the reliability of measurements when testing hypotheses, rather than just averaging measurements of multiple constituents. Conduct exploratory and confirmatory research in a way that combines self-insight and modeling skills with theory. New hypotheses are often proposed that were not originally considered, opening up new avenues for research. It is useful for experimental or survey studies, cross-sectional or longitudinal studies, measurement or hypothesis testing, within and between groups and in institutional or cultural settings. It is also easy to model (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012; Henseler, 2011; Ringle, Sarstedt & Mooi, 2012).

On the other hand, it identified the advantages of SEM to This includes the ability to model latent variables, correct for measurement errors, identify errors and their covariance structure, and estimate the entire theory simultaneously. This allows researchers to model and predict relationships between constituent variables within a hypothesis (Henseler, 2011).

Similarly, SEM techniques can be easily applied to analyzes in the medical field. Applications of SEM techniques have contributed to the study of adult and adolescent disease and substance use/abuse. Bagozzi and Yi (2012) note that there are a large number of fitness measures available to researchers, and that opinions differ widely not only on which measures to report, but also on how high the cutoffs for various measures are in practice. Given that, researchers can be overwhelmed by the conflicting information available. Ringle, Sarstedt, and Straub (2012) also found that assessing whether a particular model fits the data is one of the most important steps in modeling structural

equations, so researchers using this technique Familiarity in this area is important, he said.

SEM is usually concerned with implicit components (abstract psychological variables such as 'intelligence' or 'attitude towards brand') rather than overt variables used to measure these components. concentrate. Measurement is considered difficult and error prone. By explicitly modeling measurement errors, SEM users attempt to derive unbiased estimates of the relationships between latent components. To this end, SEM allows multiple actions to be linked to a single potential component (Pearl, 2009).

In its entirety, the teacher engagement as the dependent variable of the study, is either directly or indirectly underscored in the aforementioned review of teacher engagement in which leaders should create conducive organizational climate required to bringing about change within the institutions. From this point, the researcher found out from several readings that school principal leadership behavior stimulates and inspires school heads to have baseline information pertaining to help the school successfully balance its responsibilities and priorities. These collective readings provided the researcher a clear picture of the necessity of leading the school with innovative edge, managing and valuing diversity, and favorable individual's attitudes toward the organization.

The foregoing researches help in establishing the proponents' theoretical basis that will explore the relationship between school principal leadership behavior and strategic leadership as well as the level of instructional leadership. and teacher engagement and that structural equation modeling is utilized to look at complex relationships between variables and to reduce the relationships to visual representations. This is the most appropriate technique since it focuses more on theoretical explanation than on prediction and for the reason that there is incapability of directly measuring encompassing constructs.

E. Correlation between Measures

There is a significant correlation between the three factors. Therefore, transformative leaders are likely to be able to motivate subordinates and guide them effectively toward achieving organizational goals.

Given that leadership can generate engagement in the work of followers, teacher engagement should be encouraged. This is because teacher involvement is good not only from an individual point of view, but also from an organizational point of view (Shimadzu, 2010).

Management and leadership play an important role in faculty engagement, but it is equally important for staff to demonstrate enthusiasm for their work. Teachers should not only fulfill their professional responsibilities, but also be proud of their achievements and share the excitement of achieving their goals. The more employees feel they are developing their skills and feel more competent and in control of their work output, the more likely they are to exhibit high levels of engagement (Wiley, 2010).

Transformational leadership and commitment to the daily work of teachers. Her key finding was demonstrating a positive association between everyday transformative leadership and commitment to work. Under a transformative leader, teachers are more engaged, engaged, and able to perform better. A follower who receives support and guidance from a leader may be more engaged in their work and may find themselves in a more satisfying situation. Therefore, high levels of enthusiasm and engagement in the workplace may be related to teachers' engagement in their work (Kim, 2014).

Moreover, leadership is an important prerequisite for commitment. Leadership research shows that certain leadership behaviors of school leaders are positively associated with teacher engagement. Trust in leaders, support from leaders, and the creation of a blame-free environment are considered components of psychological safety, the conditions leading to teacher engagement proposed by Kahn (Gordon, 2013).

When school leaders promote community and equity among teachers, their commitment to the initiative becomes even stronger. Initiatives are more successful when teachers feel connected and contribute toward an identified outcome. Principals who establish learning-centered climates model curiosity and vulnerability, signaling to others that they do not have all of the answers but are eager to learn. By inviting teachers to conversations, instead of allowing teachers to sit in the back, principals are rewarded by dynamic teams who learn together and create better ideas and efforts than no one individual could produce alone (Bedarkar & Pandita, 2014).

In other words, a gap remains in understanding what leadership behaviors could affect engagement-encouraging cultures as well as the processes around which leader behaviors bring about higher levels of engagement, which is in line with the more drastic argument that there is no research directly linking leaders' behaviors and follower engagement (Xu, & Thomas, 2011).

Finally, increased leadership empowerment behaviour will result in higher levels of psychological empowerment, which, in turn, will increase work engagement. In this way, when leaders increase levels of employee empowerment, decision-making, and accountability, share information and support, and nurture employees to guide innovation, employees feel in control. come to experience. When individuals feel that their contributions are valued and that they are making a meaningful contribution (influence) to business strategy, they become more engaged (Shuck & Mogan Herd, 2012).

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilized primary research design employing Quantitative research method. It has been used to develop and apply mathematical models, theories, and/or hypotheses about phenomena (Given, 2008). The aim of the study was to develop the best model for teacher engagement.

Specifically, the study used the descriptive correlation method. The Downie and Heath (1995) descriptive association study method is a method of measuring

associations between variables at different measurement levels. In some cases, two variables are related because they are related to, or caused by, a third variable.

This is descriptive because it describes the school's level of administrative and strategic leadership, as well as its level of educational leadership. On the other hand, it is correlated because it measures the degree of relationship between the independent variables mentioned above and teacher involvement as the dependent variable.

A best-fit model was generated using structural equation modeling (SEM). It is also used as a means of translating theoretical models into path diagrams to analyze hypothetical relationships. The survey was conducted in the 2020-2021 school year. Respondents to this survey consisted of nine of her schools in Region 11, which are shown on the map on the next page. Davao Region, formerly Southern Mindanao (Cebuano:

A. *Habagatang Mindanao Island, Filipino:*

Timog and Mindanao) is an administrative region of the Philippines called Region XI. Located in the southeastern part of Mindanao, it includes the following five provinces:

Compostela Valley, Davao North, Davao South, Davao East, and the newly created province of Davao Occidental. The region is surrounded by the Davao Gulf and the center of the region is Davao City. Davao is the Hispanic pronunciation of *daba daba*, which means "fire" in the Bagobo language (Karayo is the Cebuano translation).

Additionally, many historians believe that the name Davao is a mixture of his three names given to the Davao River by his three different tribes, the first settlers to the area. The Manobo people are an indigenous people of Davao.

A river like Dabohoho. Another tribe, the Babobo, named the river Davohhaha, which means "fire", and another, the Giangan, named the river Duwau. The history of this area dates back to the times when various tribes occupied the area. The region is believed to have been inhabited by the Manobos, Mandalas and Bagobos. These are the same tribes that founded the small settlements and communities that eventually became Mindanao.

Since this study aimed to assess the teachers engagement of selected public schools, the researcher utilized sample random sampling which determined the number of schools per division.

To determine the 400 respondents appropriate for Structural Equation Modeling, the rule of the thumb was followed (Bentler, Yuan & Wu, 2010) in which the researcher like to work using the correct sample per strata in quota sampling which is 10 (Changing Minds, 2012). As shown below, the 10 divisions in Region XI were the subject of the study with the total number of 400 respondents. Davao City has the highest number of respondents of 200 with the 50%. Tagum City has 40 respondents with 10%. Davao del Sur and Compostela Valley have the same number of respondents of 30 each with 8%. Davao del Norte, Panabo City, Digos City, and Mati City have also the same number of respondents with 20 each with 5%. Island Garden City of

Samal and Davao Oriental have also the same number of respondents which is the lowest among the respondents with 10 each with 2%. Four hundred (400) teaching force of

selected private schools were involved in the study and each of them has evaluated themselves resulting to 400 samples.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Cities/Municipalities

Divisions of Region XI	Number of Schools per Division	Number of Schools	Number of Teachers
Davao City	301	20	200
Tagum City	52	4	40
Davao del Sur	51	3	30
COMVAL	50	3	30
Davao del Norte	37	2	20
Panabo City	32	2	20
Digos City	31	2	20
Mati City	30	2	20
IGACOS	17	1	10
Davao del Oriental	13	1	10
Total	614	40	400

The 10 teachers surveyed per school are in line with the Changing Minds (2012) requirement that an assignment sample of 10 per subgroup is needed to avoid sample bias. Her 400 respondents who participated in this survey were selected from her 10 faculties in Region XI by proportional sampling, using the number of schools per faculty as a reference point. Some studies and surveys include her 400 respondents as a minimum study sample size (Asten, 2008). On the contrary, some scientists argue that sample size does not depend strongly on population size, which is counterintuitive to many researchers (Sergiovane). 2015). Therefore, the number of respondents to the questionnaire is 400 for her.

After panel member approval, the researcher will perform the following steps and procedures to collect data for the study. The researchers sent a letter to the regional director of DepED Region XI requesting permission to conduct the survey in nine departments of the region, and public secondary school teachers served as respondents. Similar letters will be sent to superintendents as well as school principals regarding behavioral surveys. The researcher will submit a questionnaire and explain the purpose of ensuring her 100% recall of the research tools and equipment. As proof of honest data collection, researchers find attendance certificates from the schools involved in the study. Additionally, the researcher gets the survey questionnaire after the respondent has answered all the questions. Finally, researchers count and tabulate all data collected from respondents and subject it to statistical analysis. Statistical data are analyzed and interpreted. Conclusions were drawn from the data.

Data were analyzed and interpreted using the following appropriate statistical tools:

Average. This average was used to determine the school's level of leadership and strategic leadership, as well as its level of educational leadership. and the level of teacher involvement. This is the answer to subquestions 1 through 4.

Pearson r or Pearson product moment correlation. This was used to determine whether there was a significant association between the independent variables 'principal leadership' and 'strategic leadership' with the level of

educational leadership and the dependent variable 'teacher engagement'. This is a correlation measure used to determine the degree of relationship between two variables at least at the interval level. You can specify any value between -1.00 and +1.00. A correlation between -1.00 and +1.00 indicates perfect correlation. This will be used as the answer to subquestions #5.1, 5.2 and 5.3.

Multiple linear regression. This is a statistical tool that develops a mathematical model to predict the dependent variable based on two or more independent variables or when at least one predictor is nonlinear. It was used to determine the significance of the effect of the three independent variables on the dependent variable. This will be used as the answer for subproblem #6.

Structural equation modeling (maximum likelihood). This multivariate technique combines aspects of multiple regression (exploring dependencies) and factor analysis and is used to simultaneously estimate a large number of interconnected dependencies (Hair et al, 2010). In particular, it is used to test hypothetical models and determine the most appropriate model for teacher engagement. The following metrics were considered to assess the goodness of fit of the hypothetical model.

Chi-square/degrees of freedom (χ^2/df), goodness of fit index (GFI), standard fit index (NFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), comparative fit index (CFI), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the data collected from the teachers on Experiences in principal leadership behavior, strategic leadership, educational leadership, and teacher engagement are communicated, evaluated, and interpreted in light of research objectives. The leadership levels of school leaders are shown in Table 2. School leaders' levels of leadership are measured by school management objectives, instructional management, direct supervision of instruction in schools, responsible management, and bureaucratic management. The overall average is 4.26, which is quite high. From this, it can be seen that the degree of leadership of principals is always reflected in public elementary school teachers. Responsible

management was recorded with the most significant rating of 4.39, followed by direct supervision of school instruction at 4.33, bureaucratic management at 4.32 and management school goals at 4.22. Finally, Directive Management scored the lowest average of 4.04 for the 'Very High' rating. Four indicators were rated very high. This suggests that this measure is always evident in public school teachers.

A very high level of leadership by school principals was due to teachers' assessment of school management objectives, instructional management, direct supervision of instruction in

schools, responsible management, and bureaucratic management. Principals have demonstrated this by being able to deal with complex and rapidly changing environments and implement reforms that lead to sustained improvements in student performance. At the same time, the principal seeks to motivate the staff by helping and caring for the teachers, using constructive criticism and setting a good example of hard work. The leadership behavior of principals in non-high schools from the teacher's perspective is consistent with Chan's (2015) concept that leadership behavior is relevant to schools.

Table 2: Teacher Engagement

Indicator	SD	Mean	D.E.
Cognitive Engagement	0.50	4.16	High
Emotional Engagement	0.30	4.36	Very High
Social Engagement	0.43	4.32	Very High
Overall	0.31	4.35	Very High

Leaders authorizing subordinates to lead classrooms enable subordinates to use their individual talents in educational activities and teams to implement curriculum, and high levels of responsible management improve school efficiency. increase.

Leadership is very important to an organization. Good leaders improve morale within an organization. Even in difficult times, effective leaders can help their subordinates feel confident and happy in their position. Good leaders also contribute to employee retention. Attrition rates are high in companies, and good leadership is key to whether employees stay or leave. As you've probably heard, people don't quit their jobs, they quit their managers. Therefore, good leaders can help companies save money and increase productivity by maintaining high retention rates. Likewise, good leaders help develop future leaders. They guide and work with team members to help them grow in their role and prepare for new roles within the company. It's good for everyone. Finally, great leaders contribute to the company's bottom line.

A. Degree of strategic leadership

Table 3 shows levels of strategic leadership in setting goals, communicating school goals, monitoring and evaluating direction, and driving improvement. The overall average is 4.17, which is considered high. This indicates that strategic leadership is often strong among public middle

school teachers. Individually, supervision and evaluation of instruction was the highest at 4.21, followed by promotion of improvement at 4.18 and communication of school goals at 4.17. Framework goals achieved the lowest average scores. All indicators received high marks. This means that in public elementary school teachers, the measures are often obvious, except for supervision and evaluation instructions that the measures are always obvious.

High-level strategic leadership is recognized as contributing to setting goal frameworks, communicating school goals, monitoring and evaluating direction, and driving improvement. This is evident when school leaders create the conditions that lead to a strategic realignment of the school's vision, mission and goals for the 21st century. The leader understands that schools ideally prepare students for an unseen but not completely unpredictable future. Leaders, therefore, develop a climate of reflection that encourages school communities to reorient themselves based on their core values and beliefs about their desired future and chart a course to achieve it. to produce. It is also important for strategic leaders to monitor progress towards set goals and targets.

The manifestations are aligned with the views of several authors (Davies and Davies (2010) Hautala, Helander, and Korhonen, (2018) discuss what strategic leaders do.

Table 3: School Principal Leadership Behavior

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Management-School Goals	0.39	4.22	Very High
Instructional Management	0.49	4.04	High
Direct Supervision of Instruction in the School	0.46	4.33	Very High
Accountable Management	0.42	4.39	Very High
Bureaucratic Management	0.36	4.32	Very High
Overall	0.36	4.26	Very High

(organizational skills) and strategic leader traits (personal traits). The key activities of strategic leadership or organizational skills are creating vision, providing direction, executing strategy, influencing and developing people to

execute strategy, coordinating strategy and operations, and Develop effective intervention points (what, how, when, what to do, what to abandon), develop strategic skills, and define measures of success.

B. Level of Instruction

Table 4 shows levels of educational leadership for excellence in this area. self-awareness. strategic thinking; ability to build relationships, willingness to help others succeed, willingness to continually learn, communication skills. The overall average is 4.46, which is quite high. This shows that the level of educational leadership of public

elementary school teachers is always evident. In individual cases, communication skills reached the highest average of 4.53, followed by willingness to help others succeed at 4.51, willingness to continuously learn at 4.49, and high performance in strategic thinking and teaching, followed by the ability to Value your work, treat your colleagues, and show consideration for them.

Table 4: Level of Level of Instructional Leadership

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Framing Goals	0.45	4.11	High
Communicating the School Goals	0.41	4.17	High
Supervising and Evaluating Instructions	0.50	4.21	Very High
Promoting Improvement	0.36	4.18	High
Overall	0.37	4.17	High

These manifestations are evident in the claims of several The authors (Tyler & Boelter, 2015; Tr (Walker & Greene, 2015)) say this has the potential to inspire and stimulate educational innovation. It's about recognizing and rewarding innovation and excellence. Supporting educational innovation is also key to developing and sustaining a culture of inclusive participation. and excellence in the classroom.

Furthermore, a high level of teacher involvement is essential for full student participation and school success. Teacher engagement is a factor that contributes to improved student engagement and academic performance (Basikin, 2017). If there is a relationship between student engagement and teacher engagement, and if this correlation indicates a causal relationship between teacher and student engagement, then increased teacher engagement leads to increased teacher engagement and increases student engagement. will guide you.

C. Significance of the Relationship between School Principal Leadership Behavior and Engagement

Table 5 shows the importance of the principal-to-principal relationship.

Leadership and teacher involvement. The table shows that there is a significant association between principal leadership and teacher engagement, with an overall

correlation coefficient of 0.789, significant at the 0.05 level. It can be said that there is a significant relationship between the leadership behavior of school administrators and the dedication of teachers.

In particular, when indicators of leadership behavior by school leaders were correlated with teacher engagement, all indicators were found to be significant at the significance level of 0.05, with a correlation coefficient of 0.677 between administrators and school goals, The correlation coefficient for guidance management was 0.677. 0.862, 0.727 for direct supervision over schooling, 671 for responsible control, and 0.798 for bureaucratic control. There is a significant association between principal leadership and teacher engagement, as reflected by a p-value of 0.000 and a correlation coefficient of 0.798. This result is consistent with the findings of Thoonen et al. match. (2011), Instructional Leadership Promotes Teachers' Active Participation in Professional Development Events. Beh et al. (2013) also showed that teacher leadership has a positive impact on teacher engagement and classroom practice.

Table 5: Significance on the Relationship between Levels of School Principal Leadership Behavior and Teacher Engagement

School Principal Leadership Behavior	Teacher Engagement			
	Cognitive Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Social Engagement	Overall
Management-School Goals	.559* (0.000)	.598* (0.000)	.626* (0.000)	.677* (0.000)
Instructional Management	.537* (0.000)	.558* (0.000)	.681* (0.000)	.682* (0.000)
Direct Supervision of Instruction in the School	.638* (0.000)	.615* (0.000)	.663* (0.000)	.727* (0.000)
Accountable Management	.587* (0.000)	.515* (0.000)	.650* (0.000)	.671* (0.000)
Bureaucratic Management	.506* (0.000)	.533* (0.000)	.678* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)
Overall	.661* (0.000)	.658* (0.000)	.769* (0.000)	.798* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Leadership and teacher engagement are important and meaningful issues for teacher development. Culture has long been considered an important variable in cross-cultural studies as well. Previous researchers have found that instructors develop a shared vision of the future, supervise intellectually motivated subordinates, provide high levels of support to individuals based on their individual needs, and address individual differences. has claimed to be a person of recognition and high expectations (eg bass, 1985; Burn, 1978; Podsakoff et al., 1990).

By enabling school leaders to support teachers and teachers to support students in their educational challenges to improve academic performance, these efforts can contribute to positive change in society.

D. Significance of the Relationship between Strategic Leadership and Teacher Engagement

Table 6 shows the importance of the relationship between strategic leadership and teacher engagement. This table shows that there is an important link between strategic leadership and teacher engagement. The overall correlation coefficient is 0.746, significant at the significance level of 0.05. You may find that there is a significant correlation between strategic leadership and teacher engagement. Especially when it comes to strategic engagement

The indicators are key leadership indicators that correlate with teachers at the 0.05 level, with a correlation coefficient of 0.561 for goal setting, 0.391 for commitment to retention, 0.553 for communication of school goals, and 0.766 for monitoring and evaluation of instruction. promoted improvement. Correlation coefficient is .678

Table 6: Significance on the Relationship between Strategic Leadership and Teacher Engagement

Strategic Leadership	Teacher Engagement			Overall
	Cognitive Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Social Engagement	
Frame Goals	.462* (0.000)	.435* (0.000)	.560* (0.000)	.561* (0.000)
Communicate the School Goals	.465* (0.000)	.422* (0.000)	.550* (0.000)	.553* (0.000)
Supervise and Evaluate Instructions	.638* (0.000)	.582* (0.000)	.770* (0.000)	.766* (0.000)
Promotes Improvement	.583* (0.000)	.559* (0.000)	.636* (0.000)	.678* (0.000)
Overall	.625* (0.000)	.580* (0.000)	.736* (0.000)	.746* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

There was a significant association between strategic leadership and teacher engagement, reflected by a p-value of 0.000 and a correlation coefficient of 0.746. This result is consistent with the study of Zigarmi et al. (2017) found that strategic leaders also influence subordinates to become emotionally involved in their work and workplace. Cognitive aspects of engagement were described using terms such as enthusiasm, satisfaction, absorption, emotion, emotion and positive mental state. For example, school leaders, as change leaders, should respect teachers and pay close attention to each teacher's needs, wants and needs.

Feelings of better accomplishment and growth in school (Bass, 1985).

E. Significance of the Relationship between Instructional Leadership and Teacher Engagement

Table 7 shows the importance of the relationship between instructional leadership and teacher involvement. As can be seen from the table, there was a significant relationship between instructional implementation and teacher involvement. The overall correlation coefficient is 0.181, significant at the significance level of 0.05. There is a significant correlation between educational leadership and teacher engagement. All indicators were significant, especially with respect to education efforts. Leadership indicators correlated with her teacher at a level of 0.05, with a correlation coefficient of 0.309 for excellence in that area, a correlation coefficient of 0.137 for self-awareness, and a correlation coefficient of 0.137 for strategic thinking. 010, empathy 0.055, willingness to help others succeed 0.022, willingness to always learn 0.073, and communication ability 0.027, so it doesn't matter.

Table 7: Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Instructional Leadership and Teacher Engagement

Instructional Leadership	Teacher Engagement			Overall
	Cognitive Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Social Engagement	
Excellence in the field	.240* (0.000)	.246* (0.000)	.316* (0.000)	.309* (0.000)
Self-Knowledge	.094 (0.060)	.128* (0.011)	.133* (0.008)	.137* (0.006)
Strategic Thinking	.024 (0.639)	.015 (0.771)	-.010 (0.848)	.010 (0.846)
Ability to Build Relationship	.058 (0.250)	-.013 (0.791)	.082 (0.104)	.055 (0.279)
Willingness to help others succeed	.013 (0.796)	.022 (0.665)	-.022 (0.668)	.002 (0.970)
Continual Desire to Learn	.067 (0.181)	.075 (0.138)	.056 (0.262)	.073 (0.148)
Ability to Communicate	-.026 (0.611)	-.048 (0.339)	-.005 (0.927)	-.027 (0.589)
Overall	.151* (0.003)	.138* (0.006)	.181* (0.000)	.181* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

There was a significant association between instructional leadership and teacher involvement, reflected by a p-value of 0.000 and a correlation coefficient of 0.181. This result is consistent with Kim's (2014) study of teachers' educational leadership and engagement with day-to-day work. Their main finding was demonstrating a positive association between daily instruction and work commitment. Under a transformative leader, teachers are more engaged, engaged, and able to perform better. A follower who receives support and guidance from a leader may be more engaged in their work and may find themselves in a more satisfying situation. Therefore, high levels of enthusiasm and engagement in the workplace may be related to teachers' involvement in their work.

F. Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Five Generated Models

Table 8 summarizes the goodness-of-fit measures for the five models generated. Of the five models generated, model

5 met the criteria for the best model, showing a p-value of 000 with CMIN/DF = 6.612, RMSEA = .119, TLI = .787, NFI = .794, and CFI = 000. I was. 818 and GFI = 0.799. Model 5 is therefore the best model that describes teacher involvement. Figure 1 shows an optimal model of the direct causal relationship between the latent exogenous variables of principal leadership, strategic leadership, and instructional leadership, and the latent endogenous variable of teacher engagement. increase.

Figure 1 shows a hypothetical model that meets the criteria for an optimal model. Of the three indicators, there is no direct relationship between school management's leadership behavior and teachers' engagement. However, this model showed a relationship between educational and strategic leadership in teacher engagement. Instructional leadership striving for excellence in the field. self-awareness. strategic thinking; ability to build relationships, willingness to collaborate.

Table 8: Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Model 1

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.000
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	6.612
P-value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.799
CFI	> 0.95	.818
NFI	> 0.95	.794
TLI	> 0.95	.787
RMSEA	< 0.05	.119

Legend:

- CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
- NFI - Normed Fit Index
- TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
- CFI - Comparative Fit Index
- GFI - Goodness of Fit Index
- RMSEA - Root Means Square of Error Approximation
- Pclose - P of Close Fit
- P-value - Probability Level

Fig. 1: Structural Model 1 in Standardized Solution

Legend:

- ce – Cognitive Engagement
- ee – Emotional Engagement
- se – Social Engagement
- TE – Teacher Engagement

- msg – Management-School Goals
- im – Instructional Management
- dsis – Direct Supervision of Instruction in the School
- am – Accountable Management
- bm – Bureaucratic Management
- SPLB – School Principal Leadership Behavior

- fg – Frame Goals
- csg – Communicate the School Goals
- sei – Supervise and Evaluate Instructions
- pi – Promotes Improvement
- SL –Strategic Leadership
- ef – Excellence in the Field
- sk – Self-Knowledge
- st – Strategic Thinking
- abr – Ability to Build Relationship
- whos – Willingness to help others succeed
- cdl – Continual Desire to Learn
- ac – Ability to Communicate
- IL –Instructional Leadership

Some people succeed, but their constant desire to learn and ability to communicate are directly related to the dedication of their teachers. On the other hand, strategic leadership focused on setting goals, communicating school goals, monitoring and evaluating teaching, and promoting improvement also showed a direct correlation with teacher engagement. Teacher commitments of directly affected teachers include, among others, cognitive, emotional and

social commitments. These results can be further explained by Gordon (2013) who stated that leadership is a key requirement for engagement. Leadership research shows that certain leadership behaviors of school leaders are positively associated with teacher engagement. The elements are considered to be trust in the leader, support from the leader, and the creation of an environment without responsibility.

Khan's proposed psychological safety condition, which leads to teacher involvement.

When school leaders promote community and equity among teachers, their commitment to the initiative becomes even stronger. Efforts are more successful when teachers feel connected and contribute to specific outcomes. Leaders who create a learning-centered culture embody curiosity and vulnerability, showing others that they don't have all the answers, but they're eager to learn. By inviting teachers into the conversation rather than sitting them in the back, school leaders can benefit from dynamic teams that learn together and come up with better ideas and initiatives than any individual could come up with alone. Yes (Bedarkar & Pandita, 2014). Structural model fit measure 2

Table 8 summarizes the goodness-of-fit measures for the five models generated. Of the five models generated, model 2 met the criteria.

When evaluating the best fit model with a p-value of 000, CMIN/DF = 6.151, RMSEA = 0.114, TLI = 0.794, NFI = 0.816, CFI = 0.839, GFI = 0.876. Model 2 is therefore the best model that describes teacher involvement. Figure 1 shows an optimal model of the direct causal relationship between the latent exogenous variables of principal leadership, strategic leadership, and instructional leadership,

and the latent endogenous variable of teacher engagement increase.

Figure 1 shows the hypothesized model that satisfied the best Adjust model criteria. Of the three indicators, there is no direct relationship between school management's leadership behavior and teachers' engagement. However, this model showed a relationship between educational and strategic leadership in teacher engagement. Instructional leadership striving for excellence in the field, self-awareness, strategic thinking; ability to build relationships, willingness to help others succeed, relentless desire to learn, and communication skills are directly related to teacher engagement. On the other hand, strategic leadership that focuses on the goal framework, communicates school goals, monitors and assesses direction, and drives improvement also showed a direct correlation with teacher engagement. Teacher commitments of directly affected teachers include, among others, cognitive, emotional and social commitments. These results can be further explained by Gordon (2013) who stated that leadership is a key requirement for engagement. Leadership research shows that certain leadership behaviors of school leaders are positively associated with teacher engagement. Trust in the leader, support from the leader, and the creation of a blame-free environment are considered components of psychological safety, the conditions leading to teacher involvement proposed by Khan.

When school leaders promote community and equity among teachers, their commitment to the initiative becomes even stronger. Efforts are more successful when teachers feel connected and contribute to specific outcomes. Leaders who create a learning-centered culture embody curiosity and vulnerability, showing others that they don't have all the answers, but they're eager to learn. By inviting teachers into the conversation rather than sitting them in the back, school leaders can benefit from dynamic teams that learn together and come up with better ideas and initiatives than any individual could come up with alone. Yes (Bedarkar & Pandita, 2014).

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to public school teachers teaching in the Davao area, the leadership behavior of school principals is very high, reflected in indicators such as school management objectives, instructional management, direct supervision of instruction within the school, responsible management, and bureaucratic management. It is said that Indicators such as goal frameworks, communication of school goals, monitoring and facilitating improvement, and engagement are highly rated, with a high level of emphasis on strategic leadership. A very high level of quality was achieved in the monitoring and evaluation of instructions. Leadership Level:

“Very High, Excellence in the Field; Self-Awareness; Strategic Thinking; Ability to Build Relationships; Willingness to Help Others Succeed; Teacher engagement is very high in terms of emotional and social engagement, and cognitive engagement is also high. Correlation tests show principal leadership and teacher engagement, strategic leadership and teacher engagement, and that there was a

significant association between educational leadership and teacher engagement in the Davao Region. Key leadership behaviors, strategic leadership, and instructional leadership are important predictors of teacher engagement. Using a structural equation model to identify the best fit increases the reliability and completeness of this study as the analysis goes through the steps of model specification, model estimation and model validation. I was.

Of his five models created, model 5 best fits teacher engagement. This is the most economical model, as it adequately meets all the rules for a good fit. The success of a teacher's effort depends on many factors. In other studies, this may indicate teacher involvement in the classroom. Other factors that are more important to respondents may not have been included in the study. According to Chaudhary & Singh (2017), model fitting in this study is consistent with the ability to positively and vividly influence others through clear and powerful communication of thoughts and data. This includes organizing and organizing out-of-the-box approaches while also using your relationship skills to build committed partnerships with others. This will give you knowledge about teacher involvement. What's prevalent in specific cultures and environments helps organizers, managers, and professionals develop thriving techniques to manage the well-being of their multicultural workforce.

Recommendations Based on the above findings and conclusions, the researchers concluded that public sector teachers should improve their leadership not only in instructional leadership, but also in instructional and strategic leadership by enhancing teacher professional development and formation. also need to be improved. Recommendations for further improving teacher engagement. Additionally, with teacher involvement in mind, her DePedro code of ethics, vision and mission in public schools must be consistently adapted/re-adapted to all teachers, old and new. In addition, due attention should be given to teacher evaluation through social media, face-to-face interviews and other methods that highlight the challenges of being a loyal and committed teacher. When teachers are empowered to improve the variables above, they can be creative and expressive. Additionally, development activities may focus on developing 21st century skills for immediate adaptation to the present. In addition, we can send educators to numerous training courses and seminars to connect with new technologies and provide better learning and teaching methods designed for the future. Present strategies and approaches for addressing or implementing the 21st century skills required for various integrations. Additionally, professional development is a strategy that encourages teachers to adopt student-centered practices and expanded activities. This is especially true for development projects that require long-term business partnerships with other educators, such as educator development and mentoring networks. Governments also need to work on teacher training programs. Finally, future researchers should conduct further studies with other teacher groups, especially public schools, to confirm the findings of this study. In addition to the variables used in this study, other variables and factors that may influence a teacher's personal effectiveness may also be used.

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